

Creating of game plots as a platform for learning

Abstract: Studies of increased involvement in the learning process organized in a game form establish standards for educational plans, as a products.

One way to create such a form is implemented in a project that is partially funded under the Horizon 2020 Framework Program of the European Union, BEACONING.

The main goal of this project - is to create a system in which the participant's game success depends on his skills and knowledge, which can be transferred to the real world.

Since this is a mobile project, and end users (schoolchildren / students) will not be geographically bound to the place of the assignment, game plots have been chosen as a platform for gamification. Mechanically, the game plot is a metagame, since it contains med-term gaming goals.

During the progress in such game plot the user, associated with the game character, for successful participation in the plot events, should use the knowledge of a certain learning plan. Amount of educational material usage in the game story are determined by the teacher and the game designer at the previous stages. The direct way to interact with the player's knowledge on the subject is realized through mini-games that are setting short-term game goals for the player. To achieve such goals, the player needs the knowledge obtained at the lecture/seminar. There are also ways to deliver such knowledge through metagame itself.

I. INTRODUCTION

The gameplay itself, obviously, is more adapted learning platform to the current requirements of modern students. However, creation of each game plot is a kind of challenge, since it differs from the classical learning plan, divided onto linear lectures.

It is hard for predeveloped game plot to match all possible learning patterns that teachers or game designers will want to implement in it.

Figure 1. Game plot scenes, solving plot tasks by interacting with NPC

To solve this task, the game plot should be as flexible and varied as possible. However, given the fact that this is a meta-platform for mini-games, and player should keep his med-term goals after completion of mini-games, the game plot should remain simple.

Thus, the difficult task of forming long-term goals is shifted from the game plot to the post-game statistics of academic performance.

To set proper priorities of meta-platform development we need to evaluate statistical data of already completed learning plans and student evaluation systems.

II. GAMEPLOT DEVELOPMENT PIPELINE

Example of typical theses during creation game plot requirements list:

- Low mistake price
- Clearly defined mid-term goals (which player can achieve during current game session)
- Clear game rules (all elements, from meta-platform - till second-to-second experience should appeal to already existing positive experience - figure 2)
- Variability of player's experience:
 - *random branching in the plot*
 - *editable by teacher variables, that affect on NPC behavior*
 - *branching that depends on player's actions*
- Sufficient level of excitement, to not be boring (since game plot doesn't solve main learning goals itself, but it's only a convenient meta-platform - it's task to successfully connect places where minigames are called)
- Positive visual feedback on player's successful actions

Level	XP*	Relationship Status
Level Twelve	1860	Happily married.
Level Eleven	1800	Of course, yes, of course!
Level Ten	1740	Maintenance stage.
Level Nine	1660	Rock-solid.
Level Eight	1600	My brother really appreciated your help moving his baby grand piano.
Level Seven	1540	We got through our first major argument, woo!
Level Six	1460	Thanks for the flowers, honey!
Level Five	1400	You're my boyfriend now.
Level Four	1340	Good job with my family.
Level Three	1260	I like you enough to pass the three-month mark.
Level Two	1200	We're dating.
Level One	0	F (for "F"irst Date)

Figure 2. Example of sequence of clear short-term goals leading to mid-term goal, which is also clear, since appeals to real life experience

Creating a game plot:

- choice of topic, Lore development
- composing of a synopsis
- writing characters background
- production of assets (characters, locations)
- flow-chart of all interactions in the plot and their consequences
- detailing all the events inside each scene
- writing dialogs
- plot coding

Game plot topic should be based on events that are close to the user so that he can imagine himself at the place of the game character. Characters background should match such set of characteristics, that the player is ready to associate themselves with such a character and feel emotional involvement.

Synopsis contains branches, so player can achieve different versions of these branches, if:

- in the process of playing situations player behaves differently with the characters;
- solves the tasks posed by the plot in different ways;
- teacher sets necessary branching during lesson preparation;

The task of branching is to give the opportunity to diversify the experience gained from one game plot.

Characters backgrounds, dialogs and detailed interactions within scenes are an exclusively narrative task, without too high requirements. At this stage, should be defined all the points, where, in order to solve the plot task, player will have a short-term task in the form of a mini-game.

Figure 3. Examples of mini-games that will ask player to solve simple tasks using his knowledge on the subject

The final stage - production of content. Implementation of the already worked out game plot in the code and production of Art assets.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Usage of gamification techniques does not solve the problem of involvement by definition. All actions of the implementation of gamification should carefully planned.

Development of each game plot requires serious team of specialists and should be based on the incentives described above, which provide a greater degree of reliability.

After fulfilling the above requirements, the game plots, as a methods of gamification, have next advantages:

- Improved model of information transfer
- Constant feedback to the user
- Involvement
- Stimulation of interests
- Maintaining of attention

Given the fact that, social games have the greatest trend to growth in the gaming industry, the requirements for the degree of gamification integration and, accordingly, user involvement will grow steadily.

To meet increased requirements, the evaluation of current versions statistical data is needed. Thus, qualitative new gamification of the learning process in a year, requires releases of similar products now.

IV. REFERENCES

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